

ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY OF HERBAL PLANT EXTRACTS AGAINST INTESTINAL NEMATODES

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Abstract: Helminthiasis is one of the most important animal diseases worldwide, inflicting heavy production losses in grazing animals. The disease is especially prevalent in developing countries in connotation with poor management practices and inadequate control measures. An integrated approach is required for the effective control of helminths which includes strategic and tactical use of anthelmintics and careful management of grazing lands, including control of stocking rates and appropriate rotation strategies. Vaccinations may also play a role, as in the case of lungworms. However, problems have emerged with the use of anthelmintics, notably the development of resistance in helminths. However, the developments of resistance in helminths against commonly used anthelmintics have always been a challenge faced by the animal health care professionals. Therefore, exploitation of anthelmintic potential of plants indigenous to Indo-Pak subcontinent is an area of research interest. This paper reviews the use of some indigenous plants as anthelmintics in animals.

Keywords: Helminthiasis; Medicinal plants, polyphenols, tannins

1.Introduction: Parasitic worms (helminths) of the gastrointestinal (GI) tract are pathogens of major global importance. Over a billion people, mainly in developing countries, are estimated to be infected with soil-transmitted helminths, whilst helminth infection is also a serious problem in livestock production worldwide, causing significant economic losses and threatening food security. Helminthiasis for the most part influence in gastrointestinal tract in this manner neighborhood manifestations like epigastric agony, loose bowels, malabsorption states, a ruptured appendix ,right iliac fossa torment, rectal prolapse, gut block (volvulus), biliary obstacle (cholangitis) are generally utilized for analysis alongside foundational side effects like frailty, eosinophilia, fever, bronchospasm, pneumonitis, septicaemia, epilepsy, and so on. Based on nearby and foundational side effects distinguishing proof of worm done

by minutely stool assessment for ova, sores and parasites, and a full blood mean eosinophilia. Radiology, biopsy and Proctoscopy may likewise utilized for analysis where recognizable proof of parasite is troublesome by stool assessment. Early and customary organization of the anthelmintic medications prescribed by WHO such as mebendazole, mebendazole, diethylcarbamazine (citrate), ivermectin, levamisole, praziquantel, pyrantel diminishes the event, degree, seriousness and long term results of grime, and in certain epidemiological conditions adds to continued decrease in transmission, by and large wide scope of synthetic compound are utilized as Anthelmintic Control of helminths relies almost exclusively on a limited number of synthetic anthelmintic drugs. The limitations of this reliance on chemotherapy are the threat of parasites developing resistance to drug treatment (already widespread in some livestock production systems), the cost of drugs for small-scale farmers in developing countries and for some helminths, lack of efficacy of current available drugs [1-2]. Therefore, novel and complementary helminth control options are urgently needed.

The use of natural plant extracts as de-wormers for humans and livestock has long been practiced, however scientific validation of these practices and identification of active compounds has been lacking. Anthelmintic effects of plants are normally ascribed to secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, terpenoids or polyphenols such as proanthocyanidins [3-4], also known as condensed tannins (CT).

Approximately 2 billion people worldwide are affected by infestations with parasitic nematodes¹ of which soil-transmitted helminthiasis (STH) are most prevalent with about 1.7 billion people being infected.² The most common parasites in humans are roundworms (*Ascaris lumbricoides*), whipworms (*Trichuris trichiura*) and hookworms (*Ancylostoma duodenale* and *Necator americanus*)²⁻⁴ which commonly occur as coinfections.⁵ An infection usually starts with the ingestion of embryonated eggs by the host, or, in case of hookworms, with the infective third-stage larvae penetrating into the host's skin. Larval stages will then migrate through several tissues until they develop into adults when reaching the small intestine.⁶ Although usually not lethal, mainly adult worms that reside in the intestine cause severe symptoms, especially in children, such as anaemia and retardation in growth and cognitive development. In livestock, infestations with gastro-intestinal (GI) nematodes similarly lead to morbidity rather than mortality of the respective animals along with significant economic losses for the farmers. Particularly ruminants are affected by GI parasites of the super family Trichostrongyloidea, e.g. *Haemonchus contortus*, *Trichostrongylus colubriformis* or *Cooperia* spp.[5-7]

Currently available anthelmintic drugs include the benzimidazoles (albendazole, mebendazole) which interact with β - tubulin, pyrantel pamoate, an agonist of the nicotinic acetylcholine receptor and ivermectin that inhibits the closure of glutamate-gated chloride channels which leads to hyperpolarization. Although these drugs are generally well tolerated and effective for the treatment of STH, they are limited in number and the susceptibility among STH species has been shown to vary greatly in different populations. Another concern is the emergence of resistances: Until now there is no clear evidence for increasing drug resistances among human parasites, on the other hand resistances have been observed to a dramatic extent in veterinary medicine over the past decades. Therefore, it can be concluded that the treatment of large human populations with the few available drugs could also easily impair the effectiveness of the current treatments. Plant extracts and natural products have always been used as additional treatments or alternatives to conventional drugs and have served as valuable sources for the development of new lead structures [8, 9].

With approximately eight thousand naturally occurring different structures, phenolic compounds comprise a large group of plant secondary metabolites²¹ with the major biosynthetic groups of flavonoids, proanthocyanidins (PAC) and hydrolysable tannins (HT) and the subgroups of gallo and ellagitannins, depsidic esters of caffeic or quinic acid, phenolic acids, phenylpropanoids, lignans, stilbenoids as well as certain xanthenes and coumarins. Since polyphenols are used in the treatment of nematode infections in both, traditional medicine and modern science, this review aims at summarizing the state of knowledge on plant extracts with known polyphenolic composition and of isolated polyphenols and their respective anthelmintic effects on intestinal nematodes [10, 11].

Table 1: Various gastrointestinal nematodes that infect ruminants [12]

Oesophagus	Abomasum	Small intestines	Large intestines
<i>Cotylophoron</i> spp, <i>Gongylonema pulchrum</i> , and <i>Paramphistomum</i> spp.	<i>Haemonchus contortus</i> , <i>Teladorsagia circumcincta</i> , <i>Teladorsagia trifurcata</i> , <i>Parabonema</i> spp., and <i>Trichostrongylus axei</i>	<i>Cooperia surnabada</i> , <i>Gaigeria pachyscelis</i> , <i>Moniezia expansa</i> , <i>Nematodirus battus</i> , <i>Nematodirus filicollis</i> , <i>Nematodirus spathiger</i> , <i>Strongyloides papillosus</i> , <i>Trichostrongylus capricola</i> , and <i>Trichostrongylus vitrinus</i>	<i>Chabertia ovina</i> , <i>Oesophagostomum columbianum</i> , <i>Oesophagostomum venulosum</i> , <i>Skrjabinema ovis</i> , <i>Trichuris ovis</i> , and <i>Trichuris skrjabini</i>

Table 2. Mode of action of different anthelmintic phytochemicals [13]

S No.	Phytochemicals	Mode of action
1	Saponins	Targets the permeability of the cuticle of the parasites.
2	Benzyl isothiocyanate	Paralyses the motor activity and metabolism of the parasite.
3	Cysteine proteinases	It Contains proteolytic chymopapain and papain, which are responsible for the breakdown of the parasites' cuticle.
4	Isoflavones	Affects the glycolysis and glycogenolysis activity enzymes and calcium ions of the parasite.
5	Artemisinin	Causes the cleavage of endoperoxide bridges by iron-producing free radicals. This stresses the biological molecules of the parasite through oxidation.
6	Phenolic compounds	Uncouple the oxidative phosphorylation mechanism and disturb the glycoprotein of the cell surface, resulting in the death of the parasite.
7	Tannins	Uncouple the oxidative phosphorylation, attach to free glycoproteins of the gastrointestinal wall, and attach to the glycoproteins of the parasites causing death to the parasite.
8	Alkaloids	Paralyse the central nervous system, steroidal alkaloids, and oligoglycosides which suppress sucrose from travelling from the stomach to the small intestines; alkaloids act as an antioxidant, thus inhibiting homeostasis condition excellent for parasite development

2. Traditional use of medicinal plants

Plants have been used from ancient times to cure diseases of man and animals. This system of therapy is commonly referred as 'unani, folk, eastern, or indigenous' medicine. There are a many plants¹ which have been reported in the literature for their medicinal importance. For example, *Caesalpinia crista* (Leguminosae; karanjwa), *Melia azedarach* (Meliaceae; bakain), *Saussurea lappa* (Compositae; qust-e-shireen), *Moringa oleifera* (Moringaceae; sohanjna), *Trachelospermum jasminoides* (Apocynaceae; zard chambeli), *Butea frondosa* (Leguminosae; Dhak) have been quite commonly used. The medicinal properties ascribed to these plants include inter alia anthelmintic, antiperiodic, antipyretic, febrifugal, antiphlegmatic, and antiflatulant effects. In addition, these plants have also been used to cure nervous problems, skin diseases, cough, rheumatism, chronic fever, eczema and dyspepsia. The fruit of *Mallotus philippinensis* (Euphorbiaceae; kamala) has been used as an anthelmintic, cathartic, aphrodisiac, lithotropic and styptic. It has also been used in external applications for the control of parasitic infections of the skin, as an antiseptic for ears and systemically for urinary disorders [14-15].

The British Pharmaceutical Codex (1934) and the British Veterinary Codex (1953) cite kamala as having anticestodal properties for man and dog [16-17].

Seeds of *Butea superba* (Leguminosae; palaslata) are extensively used as sedative and anthelmintic in the indigenous system of medicine. The powdered seeds and various extracts of the plant *Peganum harmala* (Rutaceae; harmal) have been used as narcotic, analgesic, anti-spasmodic in colic and as a remedy against tapeworm infection in man and animals. *Vernonia anthelmintica* (Compositae; kali-zeeri), *Embellia ribes* (Myrsinaceae; babrung), *Psoralea corylifolia* (Leguminosae; babchi) and *Punica granatum* (Punicaceae; anar) have been reported to possess anthelmintic, laxative, expector- ant, diuretic and tonic properties. Various parts of *Lagenaria siceraria* (Cucurbitaceae; kaddoo) have been used for different ailments. For example, the pulp of its fruit is used to treat cough, as an adjunct to purgatives, as an antidote to certain poisons, and for relief from scorpion sting). Decoction of its leaves is used to treat jaundice and its seeds to treat tapeworm infections in children. *Fumaria parviflora* (Fumariaceae; pitpapra or shahterah) is traditionally used as an antidiabetic, diaphoretic, diuretic, anthelmintic. *Nigella sativa* (Ranunculaceae; kalonji) is used on empirical grounds as an anthelmintic, stimulant and diuretic. The roots of *Morus alba* (Urticaceae; toot or tut) are considered as an anthelmintic and vermifuge, whereas root bark and stem bark are reported to act as vermifuge and purgative [18-20].

Figure 1: Medicinal plants used as anthelmintics [20]

3. Methodologies for scientific evaluation of anthelmintic activity

Many of the *in vitro* investigations on anthelmintic activity of plants, their oils, or extracts have been based on their toxic effects on the earthworm, *Pheritima posthuma*. Most of the substances which are toxic to earthworms produce a primary irritation or agitation that results in the withdrawal of the worm from the neighborhood of the poison. By virtue of this effect, anthelmintics doubtless often cause expulsion of the parasite when the concentration does not rise sufficiently high to kill the worm. Some workers have also used hookworms, tapeworms and/or *Ascaris lumbricoides* for the evaluation of *in vitro* anthelmintic activity of different plant materials. *In vivo* trials have also been conducted for the evaluation of anthelmintic activity of various substances of plant origin. These included expulsion of worms from their hosts or reduction in the number of eggs per gram of feces (EPG) passed by the infected hosts compared with commercial anthelmintic treated animals [21-23].

4. Anthelmintic activity of plant extracts

Indigenous system of medicine reports a number of plants for their anthelmintic efficacy. However, rigorous scientific evaluations comparing their efficacy to commercial anthelmintics are limited.

Barbosa et al., 2023; evaluate the effects of the essential oils of *Lippia alba* chemotypes carvone and citral on *H. contortus*. Chemical characterization was performed by means of gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (GC/MS). The anthelmintic effects of the essential oils were assessed through the egg hatch test (EHT) and the adult worm motility test (AWMT) using a multidrug-resistant *H. contortus* Kokstad isolate [24].

Dicko et al., 2023; evaluate the anthelmintic activity of *Euphorbia forskalii*, in vitro bioassays were performed on three life stages of *Haemonchus contortus*. Five aqueous extracts concentrations namely 10 mg/mL; 5 mg/mL; 2.5 mg/mL; 1.25 mg/mL and 0.62 mg/mL were used for adult worm mortality tests. Egg hatch inhibition and L3 larval migration inhibition tests were studied at 5 mg/mL; 2.5 mg/mL; 1.25 mg/mL; 0.62 mg/mL and 0.31 mg/mL. A negative control PBS and a positive control levamisole 2.5 mg/mL were established for each test. The results obtained showed the presence of total polyphenols, total flavonoids and condensed tannins within the aqueous extracts of *E. forskalii*. A high and significant ($P < 0.05$) mortality rate compared to the negative control with an LC50 of 2.30 mg/mL was obtained. Inhibition of egg hatch and larval migration were high and significant ($p < 0.05$) compared to the negative control [25].

Kamran et al., 2023; investigated the pharmacokinetic behaviors of *Olea europaea* leaves extract (OLE) and its phenolic compound oleuropein in mice infected with *A. tetraptera*, in comparison with Albendazole (ABZ), a standard drug used to treat parasitic worms. Fecal flotation method was used to identify the infestation with *A. tetraptera* eggs by examining the stool samples from mice. Infected animals were divided into 7 groups. 250 mg/kg, 500 mg/kg, and 1000 mg/kg doses of OLE, 5 mg/kg and 20 mg/kg doses of oleuropein, 10 mg/kg of ABZ and tap water were orally administered by gavage for 7 days during treatments. results confirm the anthelmintic potential of OLE and oleuropein against mice pinworms and open the way for targeted extraction of bioactive compounds from plants to optimize its use in human and veterinary medicine [26].

Chakroborty et al., 2023; explore the ex vivo anthelmintic potential of synthetic derivatives of hederagenin, isolated in bulk from *Hedera helix*. Overall, MC042 was identified as the

most active molecule and the EC50 obtained from immature and adult liver fluke assays (at 24 h post co-culture) are estimated as 1.07 μ M and 13.02 μ M, respectively. When compared to the in vitro cytotoxicity of MDBK bovine cell line, MC042 demonstrated the highest anthelmintic selectivity (44.37 for immature and 3.64 for adult flukes). These data indicate that modified hederagenins display properties suitable for further investigations as candidate flukicides [27].

Pavičić et al., 2023; test the anthelmintic activity of methanol extracts of eight selected European ferns from the genera *Dryopteris*, *Athyrium* and *Blechnum* against the nematode *Haemonchus contortus*, a widespread parasite of small ruminants. *Athyrium distentifolium*, *Dryopteris aemula* and *Dryopteris cambrensis* were effective against *H. contortus* adults. In concentration 0.1 mg/mL, *A. distentifolium*, *D. aemula*, *D. cambrensis* significantly decreased the viability of females from ISE and WR strains to 36.2%, 51.9%, 32.9% and to 35.3%, 27.0%, 23.3%, respectively in comparison to untreated controls. None of the extracts exhibited toxicity in precise cut slices from ovine liver. Polyphenol's analysis identified quercetin, kaempferol, luteolin, 3-hydroxybenzoic acid, caffeic acid, coumaric acid and protocatechuic acid as the major components of these anthelmintically active ferns [28].

Kļaviņa et al., 2023; evaluate the in vitro ovicidal and larvicidal activity of extracts of tansy (*Tanacetum vulgare* L.) growing in Latvia on gastrointestinal nematodes (*Trichostrongylidae*) in sheep. The leaves and flowers of the tansy were extracted separately in 70%, 50%, and 30% ethanol and acetone. Six concentrations were prepared from each extract 500 mg/mL, 200 mg/mL, 100 mg/mL, 50 mg/mL, 20 mg/mL, and 10 mg/mL. In vitro egg hatching test and micro-agar larval development test were performed. Extracts of tansy have strong larvicidal activity. The highest percentage of larvae inhibition for most of the extracts was 100%, but for egg inhibition, it was 95.8% for the 200 mg/mL concentration of 50% acetone and 93.3% for the 500 mg/mL concentration of 50% ethanol leaf extracts. All tansy extracts had ovicidal and larvicidal activity against *Trichostrongylidae* in sheep [29].

Gonzaga et al., 2023; determine the potential anthelmintic activity of the ethyl acetate extract of *Eleusine indica* that will result in an effective reduction in fecal egg per gram (EPG) counts in naturally infected goats compared to the commercial anthelmintic levamisole. As early as 7 dpt, there was an observed reduction in the epg counts after the administration of *E. indica* extracts across all concentrations. Administering 500 mg of extract/kg body weight resulted in a maximum efficacy of 56.21%. However, the efficacy achieved was lower than that of levamisole (96.83%). The results show that the *E. indica* extract can reduce the fecal

EPG counts of naturally infected goats, thus creating a potential natural anthelmintic that can be developed further [30].

Baihaqi et al., 2023; evaluate the potential of an aqueous seed extract of *Carica pubescens* (ASE) as an anthelmintic agent during rumen fermentation and methane reduction. : In vitro study results showed that 1-5% ASE inhibited *H. contortus* after the 1st h of incubation, and 5% ASE suppressed 100% of adult *H. contortus* worms in the 5th h. Scanning electron microscopy analysis of ASE-treated worms ASE revealed damaged cuticle structures. ASE had no significant effect on pH, NH₃, volatile fatty acid, acetate, propionate, butyrate, acetate: propionate, or microbial protein in rumen fluid ($p > 0.05$). The in vitro feed fermentation results showed that ASE significantly affected methane reduction. The inclusion of up to 5% ASE in sheep diets may serve as a potential alternative anthelmintic against *H. contortus* as well as a methane reduction agent, without deleterious effects on rumen fermentation [31].

Yang et al., 2023; investigate whether phagocytic activity of microglia is involved in GSDMD-mediated pyroptosis and the pathogenesis of TLE. GSDMD knockdown augmented the accumulation of apoptotic neurons and seizure susceptibility in TLE mice. Microglia activated and transition to the M1 type with increased pro-inflammatory cytokines. Furthermore, GSDMD knockdown attenuated the migration and phagocytic activity of microglia. Of note, LPS-activated microglia attenuated seizure susceptibility and the accumulation of apoptotic neurons in TLE after GSDMD knockdown. A P2Y₁₂R selective agonist, 2MeSADP, enhanced the migration and phagocytic activity of microglia. Results demonstrate that GSDMD knockdown exacerbates seizure susceptibility and the accumulation of apoptotic neurons by attenuating phagocytic activity of microglia. These findings suggest that GSDMD plays a protective role against KA-induced seizure susceptibility [32].

5. Anthelmintic activity of plant extracts and fractions enriched in polyphenols

Within the last decade the role of tanniferous plants as anthelmintic remedies for intestinal helminthiasis has become a topic of intense discussion, especially in veterinary medicine regarding the treatment of small ruminants.

The vast majority of plants used in these studies were investigated mainly due to a substantial amount of condensed and/or hydrolysable tannins and because of their role as grazing pastures for livestock. In order to confirm the role of tannins as the active components of an

extract, polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) or polyethylene glyco are often used as precipitating agents to remove tannins from a compound mixture. However, the ability of PVP to not only remove tannins but also flavonoids from an extract should be considered when linking an activity to the presence of certain polyphenolic compounds [33].

Generally, all tannin-containing extracts seem to have different activities against nematodes at the different stages of their life cycle, from egg to adult worm. The most common anthelmintic assay performed is the larval exsheathment inhibition assay (LEIA). Exsheathment refers to the process of the ensheathed infective soil-persevering larva (usually L3) to discard its protective sheath as a requirement to infect the host organism by penetrating the digestive mucosa. An inhibition of exsheathment would therefore prevent the invasion of the host and interrupt the parasite's life cycle at an early stage. All tannin-containing extracts inhibit larval exsheathment of different nematode species (*H. contortus*, *T. colubriformis*, *Teladorsagia circumcincta*, *Cooperia oncophora*, *Ostertagia ostertagi*). [34]

On the other hand, this effect has also been shown for tannin depleted or tannin free extracts, but to a lesser extent, indicating that the observed inhibition of exsheathment is not exclusively caused by the respective tannins. Another anthelmintic activity which has frequently been observed for tannin rich extracts is the inhibition of larval migration (LMIA) of either ensheathed or exsheathed larvae. Some but not all of the tested plant extracts reduced the ability of larvae of several nematode species to migrate, even if the exsheathment had been affected. The activity of the same tannin enriched plant extracts from *Acacia gaumeri*, *Havardia albicans* and *Leucaena leucocephala* against *T. colubriformis* L3 in both assays and showed that the LEA was more sensitive in evaluating anthelmintic effects than the LMIA. [35, 36]

An assay to detect anthelmintic properties at the earliest stage of the nematode life cycle is the egg hatch assay (EHA) which has also been adopted for the evaluation of tannin containing plant extracts. Whereas some studies revealed an inhibiting activity of purified fractions of this effect could in most cases not entirely be attributed to the presence of tannins (with one exception of an extract from *L. racemosa*) or was absent at all. A compromising effect of polyphenols on other plant secondary metabolites (PSM) that are mainly responsible for the egg hatch inhibition.⁴⁵ Further anthelmintic activities of tannin-rich extracts included a reduction in the larval viability of *D. viviparous*, *T. colubriformis* as well as lethal effects against adult *C. elegans*, even though in some cases high doses of CT were required. Retardation of larval development was observed in some studies for *T. colu-*

briformis, *T. circumcincta* and *H. contortus* but not in others. Finally, a reduction of adult motility and feeding inhibition in L1 larvae of ruminant parasites can be attributed to the presence of tannins [37].

In vivo studies using plant extracts, polyphenol enriched fractions or pure compounds showed different anthelmintic effects against various nematodes. Most of the in vivo animal studies (unfortunately no clinical studies in humans have been reported) have been performed using CT preparations from quebracho (*Schinopsis* spp.) or wattle (*Acacia mearnsii* bark) and test preparations from quebracho have been shown to be well tolerated at relevant concentrations, while high dose feeding provoked intestinal ulcers. Generally, the way of administration, the respective nematode species and the host animals seem to have a major impact on the success of the treatment [38].

In most cases, a reduction of the fecal egg count (FEC) was achieved in sheep against the common ruminant parasites *T. colubriformis*, *N. battus*, *H. contortus* and *T. circumcincta* when tannin preparations were administered as drenches. However, decrease in egg excretion and fecundity of female worms (*T. colubriformis* and *T. circumcincta*) in kids but not in adult goats, pointing towards variations of the anthelmintic effects dependent on the host organism [39].

Regarding the FEC, some studies suggested nematode species residing in the abomasum of ruminants (e.g. *Haemonchus*) to be more susceptible to tannins than intestinal ones (e.g. *Trichostrongylus*), whereas others reveal a reduction in both FEC and worm burden by drenches of CT from *Acacia molissima* for *H. contortus* as well as *T. colubriformis*. Regarding the reduction of the worm burden, differences among parasite species are slightly clearer: tannin enriched extracts were more effective against intestinal (*T. colubriformis*, *N. battus*) than against abomasal species (*H. contortus* or *T. circumcincta*) in sheep as well as in goats [40].

Although most studies focused on the anthelmintic activity of tannins in ruminants, there are also few reports of effects in other animal species. Quebracho tannin was shown to reduce the FEC in mice infected with *Heligmosomoides bakeri* and worm counts of *Nippostrongylus brasiliensis* in the intestine of mice. However, no anthelmintic effect was shown against *Trichinella spiralis* in mice, although a strong activity had previously been observed in vitro. Feeding sainfoin (*Onobrychis viciifolia*) as pellets with known composition to calves led to a 50% decrease of adult worm burden for *Ostertagia ostertagi*, but interestingly not for

Cooperia oncophora, suggesting that the observations regarding the susceptibility of different ovine and caprine parasites are not necessarily true for bovine nematodes. No effect in egg excretion was observed for either parasite [41].

Tannin rich crude plant extracts and purified fractions show a wide range of different anthelmintic effects against various parasitic nematodes *in vivo* and *in vitro*. Within the *in vitro* assays, certain life cycle stages appeared to be more sensitive towards tannins (e.g. adults and L3 larvae) than others (eggs). Also, some test systems, such as the larval exsheathment assay seem to detect anthelmintic effects against the same developmental stage more precisely than others (larval migration inhibition assay). Furthermore, under *in vivo* conditions, certain differences in the susceptibility of parasites dwelling in the abomasum versus those in the intestine, as well as in the host animal can be observed. However, since these differences were not observed *in vitro*, it is likely that they are caused by differences in uptake, digestion and/or metabolism of tannins in different host animals. This could possibly also account for differences in the quality of the respective anthelmintic effect (e.g. FEC versus worm burden reduction). Regarding the potential of poly-phenolic compounds, particularly tannins, for the treatment of helminthiasis in humans, no clear statement can be made due to the absence of *in vivo* data. Reports of the traditional use of certain tanniferous medicinal plant extracts as well as the observations from *in vivo* studies in ruminants could lead to the assumption that these compounds could exert mild anthelmintic effects also in humans. However, such an extrapolation should be considered critically as there are large differences in the physiology between ruminants and non-ruminants (including humans). Therefore, controlled clinical trials are needed to draw a final conclusion in this issue [42-46].

6. Modes of Action for Anthelmintic Ethnomedicinal Plants.

It is believed that the effect of anthelmintic medicinal plants on GINs depends on phytochemical and trace mineral content, GIN neurotransmitter control, and entry routes used by ethnomedicinal plants to penetrate GINs. Different plants, used in ethnoveterinary medicine to control GINs, contain different anthelmintic phytochemicals and enzymes. It is not fully known how all phytochemicals of different plants used by communal farmers control GINs. Plants like papaya and fig trees have latex, which contains a lot of proteolytic enzymes, while pineapples have cysteine proteinases. These enzymes digest GINs. *Ficus* spp. has also been reported to have ficin. *Saba senegalensis* has compounds such as tannins, saponins, triterpene glycoside, and steroids. These compounds attach to free proteins within tubes for

larval nutrition, thus killing the GINs. While commercial anthelmintics contain one molecule acting on the parasite(s), anthelmintic plants possess numerous active molecules that act together in synergy against gastrointestinal parasites. This increases efficiency and reduces the development of resistant GINs. Aloe has amino acids such as sterols and phenols, which negatively affect the protein and body repair of GINs. While ginger's anthelmintic activity is due to gingerols, shogaols, zingerone, and paradol. these phytochemicals activate cholinergic receptors. This causes a contraction of the gastrointestinal tract, which expels parasites

7. Conclusions

Polyphenols provide a range of diverse structures with promising anthelmintic effects that can be used as an additional or alternative treatment to current standard anthelmintics as well as a base for the development of new lead structures that are urgently needed in human and veterinary medicine. A wide variety of plants are naturally available in the Indian subcontinent which possess narrow or broad spectrum anthelmintic activities. No doubt this is true in other regions of the world as well where gastrointestinal parasitism is an important problem in livestock keeping, and the availability of commercial drugs may be limited. The phytochemical analyses of these plants and controlled anthelmintic trials along with contemporary knowledge of parasite control strategies may offer new opportunities for effective and economical control of parasitic diseases.

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